

DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS BETWEEN CAMEROON AND EGYPT: A FRUITFUL COOPERATION TIES BASE ON MUTUAL AGREEMENT. A HISTORICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Long before colonization of Africa, there were extensive contacts and mutual interactions between various African countries, peoples and societies. This was the case during the period of the great empires of the western Sudan when we had very close commercial and religious relationship between black Africa and the Arab world. Colonialism and Colonial domination in such societies affected their interactions due to the creation of international borders and boundaries by colonial powers. With the attainment of independence or self-rule by most African countries, those mutual interactions were re-established, this time in the form of diplomatic cooperation. This was the case between Egypt and Cameroon. It should be noted that Egypt and its neighbours in Sub-Saharan Africa, including Cameroon, have historical and cultural ties dating back thousands of years. Successive Egyptian governments, especially since the independence have often headed south. Diplomatic relations between Cameroon and Egypt since the late 1960 have been highly fruitful, cordial and beneficial to both countries. Cameroonian and Egyptian authorities are leaving no stone unturned to see into it that their diplomatic relation is strengthened and safeguarded at the highest level. This paper therefore set out to examine the diplomatic relations that had existed between Cameroon and Egypt since the establishment of diplomatic missions between those two African countries. This cooperation is seen in the field of education, health, economy, politics, security, culture and religion.

Key words: Mutual Interactions, Diplomatic Cooperations, Cameroon, Egypt, Cultural Ties

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Bilateral relations between Cameroon and Egypt go back to a long time since the independence of Cameroon in 1960. Since then, these bilateral or better still diplomatic relations evolved to cover many fields of cooperation. The 22nd of November 1969 was the date during which the first cultural and artistic cooperation accord was sign in Cairo between Cameroon and Egypt, and it became effective on the 22nd of January 1977. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18). That was the beginning of a diplomatic cooperation ties that has lasted for almost 50 years between the two countries. It should be recalled that Egypt has long been keen on strengthening diplomatic relations with African counties. Before independence of most African Countries, Egypt served as a path or gate way for black African Muslims travelling to the holy city of Mecca to perform their pilgrimage. (Abdul M.O.A., 1982: p.121). With the attainment of independence of many Sub Saharan African Countries, Egypt strived to support their development by enhancing cooperation with them in many areas. (Hasan, 1985: pp. 28-30).

In the field of education for instance, Egypt offered scholarships to African students. Some of those students who benefited from those scholarships came from Cameroon. In the late 1960s, Africa in general and Cameroon in particular was a key focus of Egypt's foreign policy when Egypt actively supported liberation movements like the UPC party in Cameroon, and contributed to the founding the Organization of African Unity (OAU). Egypt help these movements to get their demands heard at the United Nations. (Hitti P., 1970: p. 108). It allowed many national liberation movements from Africa like the UPC party from Cameroon to open political offices in the country and use Cairo as a media headquarters to set up radio stations broadcasting in African languages. From the late 1960s, the government of Ahmadou Ahidjo establish diplomatic relations with the Egyptian government (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18). Throughout the 1970s and early 1980s, the Ahidjo government strengthened diplomatic cooperation with the Egyptian government. With the resignation of President Ahmadou Ahidjo in 1982 and the taking over by President Paul Biya, diplomatic relations between Cameroon and Egypt kept on being strengthened and were cordial and beneficial in the political, economic, social and cultural domains. These diplomatic relations were seen in the exchange of diplomatic missions between both countries as well as Egypt giving of development aids to Cameroon in different fields and domains. Fruitful diplomatic cooperation between Cameroon and Egypt have stayed unperturbed up till present. (Ngoh, 1996). This study looks at the origin, evolution and how beneficial diplomatic cooperation had been between Cameroon and Egypt.

Diplomatic relations between Cameroon and Egypt goes back to the 1960s when Cameroon got her independence with the first president, Ahmadou Ahidjo. Once diplomatic cooperation were establish between the two countries, they proceeded in the opening of diplomatic missions with residents Ambassadors in both countries capital as their countries representatives. Cameroon Ambassador to Egypt was resident in Cairo, the Egyptian capital while Egypt Ambassador to Cameroon was resident in Yaounde, the Cameroon political capital. Beginning from that moment, Cameroonian and Egyptian authorities have been cooperating in the political, economic, social and cultural domains (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

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The most strongest ties are in the excellent political relations where the two countries are keen in enhancing these relations throughout increasing coordination between the leadership of the two brotherly countries. The Egyptians endeavour to strengthen the relations with Cameroon goes back to the 20th Century where the Egyptian–Cameroonian Joint committee started its sessions aiming to cover all the fields of cooperation and explore more fields to cooperate in the future. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2016: pp. 2-15). Before given the detail analyses of diplomatic relations between Cameroon and Egypt, let us first of all locate or situate the two countries.

Geographical and Historical Presentation of Cameroon

Cameroon is situated in Central Africa, at the juncture of the Gulf of Guinea. It is bounded on the North by Chad, on the East by the Central African Republic, on the South by Congo, Gabon and Equatorial Guinea and on the West by Nigeria.

Cameroon is a country with Ten Regions and several major towns, amongst which are Yaounde, the political capital of the country, with about one million or more inhabitants. Douala, which is the major economic city has more than two million inhabitants. The other major towns are Garoua, Bafoussam, Maroua, Bamenda, Ngaoundere, Ebolowa, Buea and Bertoua. Cameroon has more than 240 tribes and two official languages which are English and French: Cameroon is a secular state. Two major religions have followers; Christianity and Islam. Animism is also widely practiced. The country has two major seasons which are the dry and rainy seasons.

Historically, Cameroon was administered by the Germans from 1884 to 1916. According to V.J. Ngoh, when the Germans were ousted from the country by the joint British and French forces during the First World War, there was a joint administration of the territory by the British and French referred to as the Condominium. From 1922 to 1939, Cameroon was a Mandated Territory of the League of Nations still administered by Britain and France. From 1945 to 1960/61, British and French Cameroons were Trust territories of the United Nations. French Cameroon got her Independence on 1st January, 1960, while British Cameroons got her own Independence on October 1st, 1961. On that very date of October 1st, 1961, Reunification of British and French Cameroons took place under the United Nations supervision.

Geographical and Historical Presentation of Egypt

Egypt is an independent state or country in North Africa on the eastern Mediterranean. It has a surface area of 386,110sq.m. The current population of Egypt is 102,711, 94 as of Sunday, September 13, 2020 based on world meter elaboration of the latest United National data. A population made up of Beduoin nomads, and Nubians of mixed Arab and Negro blood. The Capital of Egypt is Cairo. The great majority of the population is Muslims. Egypt was a Semi-independent state with a hereditary viceroy or kledive, and under Turkish sovereignty, from 1841 to 1916. From 1922 it was occupied by British troops and under British administrations. In 1914, a British protectorate was declared and the Pro-German khedive was deposed. In 1922, the Pro-British Sultan Fuad was proclaimed king. The Anglo-Egyptian treaty of 1936 recognized Egyptian sovereignty but gave to the U.K. the right to maintain a garrison on the Suez Canal (Florence Elliott, 1973: 141-142).

A coup d'etat by a group of officers on 23 July 1952 led to the abdication of king Farouk and the eleven-month reign of his infant Son, Ahmed Fuad II. Civilian titles such as Pasha were abolished. Negotiations began with the U.K. on the question of the Suez Canal zone and in 1954, the 1936 treaty was terminated, it being agreed that all British forces were to leave the Zone by June 1956.

General Mohammed Neguib declared a Republic in June 1953 and was President until 1954 when he was relieved of all his posts. Presidential powers were then vested in the council of ministers. Colonel Gamal Abdel Nasser became Prime Minister, and in June 1956 became President when the council was dissolved. Gamal Abdel Nasser should be noted nationalized the Suez Canal in 1956. On the 1st of February 1958, the country was known as the United Arab Republic. The name was later changed following a referendum to approve a new constitution and the proposed accession of Egypt to the Federation of Arab Republics (Florence Elliott, 1973: 142-143).

Cameroon-Egypt diplomatic ties reinforced

Cameroon and Egypt share a very good diplomatic history. According to Sherif Salah Eldin Elleithy the Egyptian ambassador to Cameroon in 2016, interviewed by Cameroon Tribune, Cameroon-Egypt diplomatic relations goes back to 1960, when the former got her independence. This cooperation ties had evolved from the 20th to the 21st centuries. The bilateral ties was manifested within the Egyptian-Cameroonian Joint committee. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

It should be noted that Cameroon hosted the sixth session of the joint committee on April 2010, during which the two countries signed a number of agreements and memorandums of understanding in the fields of basic education, higher education, technical support, political consultations, trade, investment, communication and energy. Egypt hosted the follow up committee on October 2013 to continue the coordination and increase the scope of cooperation between the two countries. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18). Nowadays, Egypt and Cameroon are preparing for holding the 7th session of the joint committee which will take place in Cairo with the goal of promoting bilateral relations and enhancing cooperation between the two countries in all fields.

It should be recalled that Cameroon and Egypt have many fields of mutual cooperation. According to the Cameroon Tribune of 12th August, 2016, the technical assistance offered by the Egyptian Ministry of foreign Affairs through the Egyptian agency of Partnership for Development (EAPD) is considered one of the main fields of cooperation between the two countries. The EAPD offers more than 40 training courses annually to the Cameroonian government in order to participate in capacity building of the Cameroonian Personnel in many fields, among them: Health, energy, agriculture, tourism, trade audit and security. In addition to that, Egypt offers a number of scholarships, offered by the Egyptian Ministry of Higher Education and al-Azhar University for the Cameroonian Students. Also, there is Al-azhar mission that is serving in Cameroon counting 35 teachers in many Cameroonian regions spreading the moderate teachings of Islam to the Children and Youth in order to eradicate the extremism and terrorist ideology (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2016: pp. 2-15).

As Ambassador Sherif Salah Eldin Elleithy put it, the mutual visits of the officials of Egypt to Cameroon and the Cameroonian officials to Egypt are considered strong signs of the willingness of the two countries to boost their relations. In this regards, we also have several visits of the Cameroonian officials to Egypt, among them the visit of the representative of his Excellency the Presidency of the Republic, Mr. Ayang Luc to the inauguration ceremony of the new Suez Canal project, the participation of several Cameroonian officials headed by Minister Louis Paul Motaze at the Economic Forum "Investment in Africa 2016". (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2016: pp. 2-15).

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Besides, the visits of their Excellencies, Ministers of culture, water and Energy, Environment, Small and Medium size Enterprises and Housing and Urban. Development to Egypt. And on the side, the visit top Yaounde of The President of the Association of African Sports confederations (UCSA) General-Ahmed Nasser, and the President of the African –Asian Writers, Mr. Mohamed Salmawy, and recently the President of Egyptian post authority, Mr. Essam El-Sagheer. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2016: pp. 2-15).

According to the Egyptian Ambassador to Cameroon in 2018, Medhat Mohamed Kamal Elmeligy, in an audience granted to him by the Minister Delegate at the Ministry of External Relations in charge of Cooperation with the Islamic world, Adoum Gargoum, on the 07 of June 2018, the launched Cameroon-Egypt relations as diplomatic relations that is fruitful and is steadily taken an upper trend. The relation according to the Ambassador in the Cameroon Tribune of 7th June 2018, that started in 1960 has blossom in leaps and bounds. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18). The Ambassador equally presented his support to the Cameroon government ahead of the continental tournament, the African Cup of Nations that Cameroon will be hosting. As he put it, together with the other 23 teams qualified for the competition, Egypt will be present to actively participate. Cameroon according to Ambassador Medhat Mohamed is remarkable for its hospitality and professionalism. He went further to say that Cameroon and Egypt cooperate in wide range of disciplines such as capacity building through the different trainings offered Cameroonians, Participation in development through construction works by Arab contractors, support in the management of humanitarian crises and other social advancing initiatives. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

The newly designated Ambassador of Egypt to Cameroon, Dalia Fayeze Farag Ghubrial has handed the advance copies of her accreditation documents to the Minister of External Relations, Mbella Mbella. According to Eulalia Amabo, this was during an audience the latter granted the former on March 3, 2022 at the Ministry of External Relations. Void of declarations, the audience served as a platform of contact exchange for a greater cooperation ties between the two countries as Dalia Fayeze Farag Ghubrial now heads the diplomatic representation of Egypt in Cameroon. She replaces Medhat El Meligy who came to the end of his diplomatic stay and bade farewell in January this year .(Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

The new Egyptian Ambassador to Cameroon H. E. Mme Dalia Fayeze Farag Ghubrial paid a working visit to Cameroon's minister of higher education, Jacques Famme Ndong in March 2022. As earlier said, the two personalities discuss friendship and cooperation ties between Cameroon and Egypt. Emphasis was laid on scholarship and internship programs offered by the Egyptian government to Cameroonian student. During that visit, the two personalities again made reference to the period when Cameroon and Egypt cooperation ties began. The 22nd of November 1969 was the date during which the first cultural and artistic cooperation accord was sign in Cairo between Cameroon and Egypt, and it became effective on the 22nd of January 1977. (Beshir M., 1982: p. 88). That was the beginning of a diplomatic cooperation ties that has lasted for almost 50 years between the two countries. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

On the 11 of April, 2022, Ambassador Dalia Farag was also received in audience by the Cameroon Minister of the Economy, Planning and Regional Development, Alamine Ousmane Mey. During that audience, both officials discussed on some specific areas through which the cooperation between Cameroon and Egypt could be fostered. These included amongst others the areas of woods transformation, trade, exportation and agriculture. According of Emmanuel Kendemeh of Cameroon Tribune, MINEPAT used the opportunity to thank Egypt for its support in various projects in Cameroon naming amongst others the support of Egypt in the Islamic Institute in Ngaoundere. He also expressed the desire to nurture a more diversified cooperation between Cameroon and Egypt in a bit to make it more resilient in the face of difficult times.

It was equally a firsthand opportunity for the MINEPAT to hand over the National Development Strategy 2021 2030 to the Ambassador of Egypt. Speaking to the media after the meeting, H. E. Mme. Dalla Faye Farag explained that her country will start to discuss on how they can cooperate in putting this strategy on the field and expressed the hope that the next time they will have this meeting; it will be to witness the opening of the new project and the new cooperation between the two countries. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

The new Ambassador, Dalia Faye Farag was also received in audience by the Prime Minister, Joseph Dion Ngute on June 8, 2022 in the capital, Yaounde. According to Eulalia Amabo, this was a maiden star building discussions with the Cameroons Prime Minister. After the discussions, the Egyptian diplomat told the press that she used the occasion to hand to Prime Minister Joseph Dion Ngute a letter from the Prime Minister of Egypt. On the focus of their discussions, it was based on the new Egyptian Ambassador being brief about the internal affairs of Cameroon. She went further to specified that Prime Minister Joseph Dion Ngute briefed her about the political, economic and security affairs in Cameroon.

Egypt to help Cameroon in fighting terrorism

Egypt Ambassador to Cameroon in 2016, Sherif Salah Eldin E. reassured Cameroonian authorities of Egypt's full support in fighting terrorism. He appreciated Cameroon's President Strategy in fighting terrorism. He also assured the Cameroonian authorities of Egyptian readiness to cooperate with Cameroon and provide it expertise on the fight against terrorism. Taking into consideration that Egypt condemns all acts of terrorism around the world. Egypt also appreciated the active policy of his Excellency President Paul Biya, in maintaining peace in Central-African Region, as well as hosting tens of thousands of refugees from Central African Republic and Nigeria. Egypt provided humanitarian aids to the Cameroonian government in October 2015, included foodstuffs and tents to face the crisis of the refugees and displaced people in Cameroon. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

The Egyptian government through her diplomatic mission in Cameroon are ready to provide certain materials as well as training expertise to Cameroon in the field of security. The Egyptian government knows very well that terrorism is a global issue or phenomenon. As such, a single country cannot fight against it. That is the reason why Egypt try as much as possible to make available her assistance to Cameroon at the level of Intelligence gathering, Information Sharing, financial assistance, technical assistance, training and global condemnation of terrorism. (Josy, 2017: pp. 3-13).

One of the region where Egypt has been supporting Cameroon to fight against terrorism is the Far North Region; in the fight against the Boko Haram terrorist organization. To begin with, Egypt through her diplomatic mission in Cameroon has left no stone unturned to condemn the terrorist actions of Boko Haram. Taking into consideration that Egypt is overwhelmingly an Islamic country, they try as much as possible to preach moderate Islam and religious tolerance. According to Emmanuel Kendemeh of Cameroon Tribune, Egyptian authorities are against the type of Islam propagated by the Boko Haram terrorist organization. Egyptian Clerics sent to Cameroon from Al-Azhara University are advised by the Egyptian authorities to teach and preach moderate Islam, in Cameroonian Schools and Mosques. The Egyptian clerics in collaboration with their diplomatic mission and the Cameroon government are advice not to teach or preach Islamic extremism or fundamentalism. Regarding the Socio-political and economic crisis in the North West and South West Regions, the Egyptian government through her diplomatic mission is encouraging dialogue and not arms conflict to resolve the problem. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

Egypt's aids to Cameroon in the field of Urban Development

Urban Development and infrastructure is another area Cameroon stands to gain from Egypt thanks to the two countries diplomatic cooperation or relations. Egypt has great experiences in the fields of urban development, constructing socio-economic infrastructure, including hotels, roads and social houses. The Cameroonian government had shown interest on benefiting from the urban housing and infrastructure sectors. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18). The Egyptian government welcomed the cooperation between the two countries in this field. That was the purpose of the minister of Housing and Urban Development visit to Egypt where his Excellency met his Egyptian counterpart and signs a memorandum of understanding in this concern which enhances the bilateral relations between Egypt and Cameroon in this important field. As such, there is an Egyptian outstanding company, the Arab contractors, working in the field of construction and infrastructure, provide all the support and expertise to the Cameroonian brotherly government. The Arab contractors had successfully implemented her footprints in Cameroon especially in the field of infrastructure and building construction. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

Egypt has a big tourism sector with more than three million workers, given the diversity of tourism places and resorts and monuments that Egypt has. This sector provides a percentage of 11% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Egypt. In this regards, Egypt and Cameroon signed a memorandum of understanding in the field of Tourism in 2008. Knowing that the Egyptian Agency in Partnership for Development in Collaboration with Egyptian Ministry of Tourism had offered earlier in 2016 two training courses in the field of development of Tourism to the African countries and Cameroon was among the participants in these training courses. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2016: pp. 2-15).

Egypt has been always a part of the African continent as one of the main actors on the African arena. Besides, the historical relations that Egypt has with its brotherly African countries, His Excellency Abdel Fattah Al-Sisi, President of the Arab Republic of Egypt has launched a new strategy with the aim of increasing Egypt's relations with Africa in all fields and to make Africa one of the main dimensions of Egypt's foreign policy in order to restore our all-time role at heart of the African continent. (Akinsaya, 2010: pp. 2-19). This strategy gave a push to the Egyptian-Cameroonian relations for the past two years in the light of the common vision of the leaderships of the two countries towards the necessity to enhance these relations. In addition to the keenness of Egypt held the "Investment in Africa 2016" Economic Forum hosted by his Excellency President Abdel Fattah Al-SiSi which aimed at strengthening the ties that combine the Africa countries and increasing the volume of trade between them as well as raising the flow of foreign direct investment to the African countries.

Egypt is keen on seizing its non-permanent membership at the United Nations Security Council to reassure its belongings to its African roots. Egypt is still throughout this membership playing its historical role defending all the cases related to the African countries especially with the Egyptian membership of the African Union Peace and Security Council which permits Egypt to play a significant role in coordination between the two councils towards the African continent cases and problems. (Akinsaya, 2010: pp. 2-19).

Arab Contractors and Cameroon

Arab contractor is an Egyptian construction company established in 1955 by Osman Ahmed Osman. Ahmed Osman is an Egyptian entrepreneur and politician who served as Egypt's Housing Minister under Sadat's presidency. Worth noting is the fact that Arab contractors was nationalized after the Egyptian Revolution of 1952. The company participated in the construction of the Aswan High Dam and also aided the War efforts during the 1973 war. (Hopkins A.G., 1973: pp. 10-80).

Arab contractors has been involved in the construction of several government buildings in Egypt. According to Akinsaya (1973: pp. 1-17), the company also owns a football club, El Mokawloon S.C. that plays in the Egyptian Premier's league. Today, El Mokawloon El-Arab is one of the largest companies in the entire Middle East and North Africa with big projects not only in Egypt, but also Morocco, UAE, Algeria, Libya, Lebanon and Kuwait. (Hopkins A.G., 1973: pp. 10-80).

Arab contractors in Cameroon

Arab contractors are not just limited to the Middle East and North Africa. They also carried out investment ventures or constructions in black Africa. A glaring example is their multiple construction done and others undergoing in Cameroon. According to Eulalia Amabo, on the 10th of May 2012, Arab Contractors Ltd Cameroon won a 60 million US\$ contract in 2012 included the construction of a ring road in Sangmelima, about 150 Km from Yaounde, with a total value of 34 million US\$ besides, manufacturing and supplying of Sand Crusher to Mvulu Dam 300km from Yaounde with a total value of 26 million US \$ 2.6 billion. Arab contractor's projects in the three African countries vary between roads, ports and infrastructure works. The announcement was made following a tour by Arab contractor's Chairman Mohsen Salah to visit the company's projects in Cameroon, Nigeria and Equatorial Guinea. The Chairman of the Company also intended to attend their general assembly to review the company's business volumes' in those countries. Arab contractors once more should be noted is one of the leading construction companies in the Middle East and Africa, and for decades has helped boost ties between Egypt and other African nations; with the notable case of Cameroon. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2016: pp. 2-15).

The volume of Arab contractor's business portfolio in Cameroon is exceeding US\$ 100 million, including Yaounde road project and the rehabilitation of Dgalobo district at value of US\$ 113 million. The most important project undertaken by Arab contractors in Cameroon is the Bikoula and Djoum road in the Southern Region of Cameroon. This road section is part of the cross-border road Sangmelima-Ouessou. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18). As a matter of fact, the road is divided into four sections or part. We have the first one beginning from Sangmelima to Mengong which is estimated at 74 km. Then, the second one from Sangmelima to Bikoula estimated at 65km. The third one from Bikoula to Djoum estimated at some 38km. and finally, the fourth one beginning from Mintom-lele-Ntam leading to Mbalam estimated at some 68km. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18).

From the above analysis, it can be seen that Cameroon and the Egyptian construction company, Arab contractors are engaged in a very fruitful, win-win collaboration. Cameroon is gaining so much from the technical expertise or know-how of the company in infrastructural development, while Arab contractors are also gaining financially from the Cameroon government. These cooperation ties is also helping a lot in strengthening the diplomatic relations between Cameroon and Egypt. (Eulalia Amabo, 2018: pp. 4-18). Looking at the number of construction projects carry out by Arab contractors in the Middle East and Africa and the immense experience that the Company has, it will be very important for Cameroon to further re-inforce and strengthened cooperation ties with Arab contractors. This will enable Cameroon to benefit more from the technical assistance or expertise of that Egyptian multinational construction company called Arab contractors.

CONCLUSION

Diplomatic cooperation ties between Cameroon and Egypt as we said dates back to the 1960s. This diplomatic ties have been fruitful and beneficial to both countries especially for Cameroon. This is seen on the different aids in cash and kind that the Egyptian government have been giving to Cameroon. The bilateral cooperation is also seen in the different diplomatic missions who are sent to represent both countries as diplomatic missions or Ambassadors of their respective countries. The cooperation ties is also manifested in the political, economic, social and cultural domains. Making a balance sheet of this cooperation ties, from all indication, it has been a win win diplomatic cooperation ties. The Cameroonian and Egyptian authorities are trying all their best to see into it that the diplomatic cooperation continue being strengthened and maintained. Egypt clearly has a growing interest in Cameroon as shown by its increased involvement in initiatives aims at fostering cooperation ties. These initiatives are in the political, economic, social and cultural domains. Cameroon also has a fervent wish for the diplomatic cooperation to continue looking at the amount of aids she receives from the Egyptian government.

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